

ECOBULK

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

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End user and stakeholder platform

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable, titled “D6.3 Report on Stakeholder and End-User platform”, is a description of the purpose, features and requirements of the Ecobulk’s Stakeholder and End-User platform. It starts with an overview of the context at which the platform is implemented and developed, followed by the main constraints applicable, and ends with a full description of the implemented functionalities which are derived from the use cases.

The Ecobulk Stakeholder and End-User Platform has been developed in the framework of the project, and serves as demonstrator of its software services and databases. However, the Platform has been conceptualized and structured as an integral tool to support circular economy models for composite materials and products, including greater re-use, upgrade, refurbishment and recycle of such products, parts, and materials.

Therefore, the Ecobulk Stakeholder and End-User Platform is itself a pilot test for digital services and data bases used in circular economy.

Although this report is not intended to be a software requirements specification, it does follow some of the recommendations and structure presented on IEEE 830 standard guidelines to enhance the readability and facilitate the comprehension of the readers.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The *WP6: Design of the systems, services and databases* of the Ecobulk project integrates a software system that compiles different tools as shown in Figure 1. Those tools and services are developed by different partners of the Ecobulk's consortium and their interaction is the one depicted in the aforementioned picture. To make them available for the specific actors and stakeholders, the software system involves a platform built on top of them that serves different functionalities depending on the role of the user, making a clear distinction between a stakeholder and the different kinds of end-users for the Ecobulk products which would have different interest and needs.

The End-User & Stakeholder platform would allow the different actors of the value chain (e.g., designers, manufacturers, distributors, dismantlers, etc) to share information (e.g., material properties, use patterns, etc) and services through a unified web frontend and, at the same time, the platform will implement typical circular economy strategies to encourage the end-user of goods to engage with the circular economy principles.

Figure 1: Overview of Ecobulk's software systems.

1.1 Description of the document and purpose

The aim of this document is to describe the specifications, requirements and functionalities of Ecobulk's end-user and stakeholder platform. To do so, the problem statement is defined in detail to then focus in the platform features and their implementation.

1.2 Intended audience

This document was initially created for application developers as a guide during the platform implementation stage. It has supported its deployment and management providing the reference for the software and hardware requirements, along with the necessary external interfaces.

The document is also used by the Ecobulk consortium as the specifications for the end-user and stakeholder platform and it supports the exploitation phase of the software presenting its functionalities and requirements.

Additionally, this document will be part of the D6.3 deliverable together with the End-User and Stakeholder platform itself that is located in the following web direction:

<https://eushp.ecobulk.upc.edu/welcome>

1.3 WPs and Tasks related with the deliverable

The End-User & Stakeholder platform is part of the *WP6: Design of the systems, services and databases*. This WP groups a set of services to enable interaction between actors, the databases to store information, and the capabilities to analyse/process that information. Figure 2 presents the interdependencies between the work packages of the project, where the different flows of information through databases and services in WP6 can be observed.

Figure 2: Work packages interdependency.

2 OVERALL DESCRIPTION

This chapter aims to review the generalities and high-level aspects of the platform aiming to provide a full description of its intended features and design constraints.

The developed platform is envisioned as a platform capable of promoting the circularity of goods by means of increasing the amount of information shared by the actors involved in the circular chain. To do so, it makes use of several intelligent software modules or services developed by Ecobulk WP6 partners.

The end-user platform implements strategies related to reusing, repairing, refurbishing, recycling and disposing to encourage the end-user to engage with the circular economy principles, extend the life of products and favour the efficient use of resources. Therefore, the End-user Platform will focus mainly on the engagement and interaction with end-users. The definition of end-user is broad, and it covers from individuals and organisations using products to stakeholders along the value chain (e.g. retailers, collectors, etc). Hence, this section will also try to establish these users to give more context to the project software-related systems.

2.1 Product Perspective

The End-User and Stakeholder platform provides a unified web frontend to access a set of services and ICT tools developed by Ecobulk partners. Through the platform, users involved in the Ecobulk project have access to the information generated by the different tools. For instance, it connects designers and manufacturers through the information of materials and products acceptance rates; and retailers with waste managers for assessment of product life extension and product end of life strategies.

The implemented services exposed in the End-User and Stakeholder platform are:

- Database: the database service consists of the GRANTA Database management system which includes support for Designs, Materials and Test Data, and Processes. The system is described in detail in D.6.4

- Tracking, Labelling and Reverse Logistics: the service is composed of a tracking and labelling system and a reverse logistics evaluation and recommendation tool. The system is described in detail in D.6.2
- Decision Support System: the service supports decision making regarding the optimal actions to take at the post-usage collection point in order to increase the circularity of the supply chain. The system is described in detail in D.6.5
- Quality Assurance System: the service provides the Protocols, Actuation Procedures and Manufacturing Good Practices. It also serves as a material validation tool using the laboratory test batches as input. The system is described in detail in D.6.6.

2.2 Value chain and high-level requirements

This section is intended to review the high-level definition of the functionalities that the platform has apart from the services developed in WP6. The preliminary requirements for the platform were defined through the analysis of the circular value chain envisioned to close the loop in the construction sector demonstrator.

Figure 3: Ecobulk value chain description.

The value chain configuration in Figure 3 is hypothetical considering that (1) the products and solutions proposed by CONENOR (recycling and utilization of GFRP waste as reinforcing material fraction in manufacturing circular thermoplastic composites for construction sector) are new with no market uptake as so far; (2) CONENOR is a R&D SME only acting as OEM for the sake of the project.

Following the waste hierarchy principles, the end-user may want to sell/give away/dispose (pay) the assembly either to:

- a) Another end-user for reuse in the same application.
- b) Another end-user willing to reuse/repurpose assembly/component in other applications (e.g. professionals, such as designers/architects/constructors that are looking for ways to reuse products and components in architectural/engineering projects).
- c) Waste collection and management companies interested or contracted to take back used GFRP composite products or other composite waste materials from refurbishment or “strip out” projects.

There are a few options/routes for the assembly when reaches its end of life:

- If geographically close, it could go straight back to the original converter.
- If not geographically close, it could go back to another converter.
- There could be a role for a waste collection/sorting/shredding company to aggregate waste from different places and shred to make transport easier (especially for large EoL items) and then transport to the converter.

Based on the preliminary analysis the following points have been identified as key issues to be addressed by the software platform:

- **Material sourcing platform:** there needs to be a material exchange platform for selling EoL or production waste (e.g. GFRP waste) to create opportunities for those looking for ways to get rid of waste (EoL or GFRP waste owners/processors) either at no or low cost or even being paid back, if possible; and those with capabilities to process primary and secondary (recycled/waste) materials (converters) that are looking for low-cost and high-quality raw materials.

- **Material passport:** To enhance the material exchange and recovery at the EoL, the platform needs to store material, component and product information (e.g. material content, weight/volume, location, origin, composition, grade, toxicity, embedded energy, carbon emissions, etc.).
- **Labelling and tracking:** labelling and tracking are essential to connect material passports with real-life assets and follow them through value chains.
- **Reverse logistics:** while the new composite products could be sold worldwide, return logistics should be quite local (due to the low value of materials). A list of options with costs, time and possible environmental impacts (depends on the location of waste products) should be provided for the converters.
- **Marketplace for the end-users:** the platform should allow the end-users to resell or give away products for the same purposes, but at the same time it should allow engaging other users (e.g. architects/designers and constructors) to look for alternative applications in line with the Urban Mining concept (reusing/repurposing) before grinding and compounding the materials again or disposing of them (downcycle).

A similar study can be carried out for the furniture sector giving similar outcomes. Hence, the aforementioned functionalities are the ones that will be implemented specifically for the End-User and Stakeholder platform.

2.3 User profiles

This section reviews the different actors that interact with a circular economy model from the point of view of their role. The document D6.1 Report on user and system requirements and reference architecture identifies the following list of circular chain platform stakeholders:

- Designers, FEA engineers.
- Material experts (research or test centres, QA).
- Manufacturers.
 - Components / pieces manufacturers.

- Assembly / final product manufacturers.
- Logistics.
 - Transport, warehouse.
 - Outlets.
- Collection.
 - Collection and routing centres.
 - Reverse logistics.
- Re-manufacturers.
 - Product repair.
 - Product refurbishing.
- Waste handlers.
 - Dismantlers, material recovery, recovered material producers.
 - Waste disposal (circular leakage).

A company may act as more than one role, but separating them helps to identify the needs and requirements of such actors. Together with them, there is a broader category corresponding to the circular-chain user that makes use of the manufactured products and should get access to the public-facing functionalities of the platform but not to the stakeholders' related functionalities.

2.4 Design and Architectural Constraints

During the development of the software modules, a distributed approach was chosen and described in detail in Section 3.1 of D6.1. This distributed approach, or service-oriented architecture, implies that multiple pieces of software collaborate to provide the functionalities whereas acting as independent services. This approach requires the development of a unified web frontend to ensure seamless access, easier user-experience and communication between the different tools.

2.4.1 General functionalities

The main functionalities of the end-user and stakeholder platform are related to the referenced user stories defined on D6.1. To ensure the correct delivery of those functionalities and to improve the behaviour of the platform, some general functions have been integrated.

Authentication

The platform involves a shared user database that implements a Cross-Domain Single sign-on (CDSSO) mechanism for transferring user credentials across multiple secure domains. Therefore, the management and control of user credentials would be centralised. Basic forms to sign-in would be implemented within.

User information

Additional information about the user is required to detail the user profile and be able to redirect the traffic to the different linked services. This information would be part of the centralised sign-on service in order to avoid duplicity and to be able to define access rules for the different services.

Redirect traffic to exposed services

The platform would act as a gateway to expose the services and based on the authentication procedures it would redirect the user to the services they are granted access to.

Service usage analytics

The platform would involve functionalities to track the activity of the users and analyse the usage patterns. These functionalities will cover the tracking of the frequency access to the platform modules and features using off-the-shelf web analytics tools such as google analytics.

2.4.2 Operating Environment

Given the architecture type, each of the services linked to the End-User and Stakeholder Platform may have different needs and dependencies, thus they will require different operating environments. In this section, only the execution environment for the platform itself will be reviewed. The reader is referred to the deliverables related to other services to read about their execution system.

The End-User and Stakeholder platform frontend has been implemented in Typescript, using Angular as its framework. It will be served from the Static Web Applications Services provided by Azure, Microsoft, a specialized service for web hosting of static web content, as HTML, CSS and JS, world-wide with a good performance.

Backend services had been developed to be deployed on a Linux LTS 64bit platform server using an architecture based on micro services, designed to be encapsulated in containers. These services have been developed in JavaScript, running over Node.js using Express as its framework, deployed into Web Applications Services on Azure.

The single-sign-on (SSO) system has been developed following the same constraints. MongoDB database software has been used for the required persistence of the user data, and Pug has been used as the mark-up language for the frontend, together with PugJS as HTML rendering engine.

The transport protocols used in the platform will be JSON for plain text data and binary files will be sent over HTTP.

3 SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS AND FEATURES

After reviewing the formal aspects and general functionalities of the platform, this section's objective will be to evaluate the requirements in terms of features and functionalities. As seen in section 2.1.3, the platform makes a clear differentiation between the stakeholder of a circular economy chain (understood as any business which takes part in one or more steps in the lifecycle of a product) and the final end-user that utilize the product and is willing to participate in a more circular life chain. For this reason, this section is divided into functionalities that apply to both kinds of user and functionalities specific to each one. To identify these functionalities, the development of the platform follows the traditional approach of the use cases as presented below.

The rest of this section consists of the currently implemented version of the functionality view together with the sequence diagram associated with it, to facilitate the reader the understanding of the logic behind each of the functionalities.

3.1 Use Case analysis

The requirements for the platform were compiled using more detailed user stories for each of the proposed profiles, which define the needs of end-users and stakeholders using the platform. The user stories take a predefined format, specifically "As an [actor] I want to [action] so that [reason]". The detailed user stories are presented in the Annex A.

These profiles have been constantly evaluated according to the different use cases defined on the project, as well as the contributions from the project partners.

In the table below, a summarized description of the different features and characteristics required to handle the different actions described on the user stories can be found, which are exposed in detail in the following sections.

Non registered user

- Product scanning and details
- Product opinion survey fulfill

Registered user

- User verification and management
- Ecobulk product search and details
- Ecobulk waste converters search

End user

- Products requests
- Own instances management
- Instance status and maintenand survey fulfill
- Marketplace search, publish and contact

Stakeholder

- Ecobulk raw materials, composites and designs search and details
- User instances management
- User requests management
- Surveys management

Table 1: Required features and services to handle the user stories defined functionalities.

3.2 Functional requirements

In this section the different services offered by the End Users and Stakeholder Platform are defined, describing the developed software components used to achieve each functionality.

3.2.1 General functional requirements

This section describes some common functionalities that are used along all the application.

Terms and conditions

End Users and Stakeholder Platform is required to be deployed under its Terms and Conditions, as defined in the regulation section. All registered end users and business users are required to accept the Terms and Conditions, which are easily at any moment at the application.

Access to terms and conditions is available at the application footer or at the about section in mobile view.

Requests

Communications between different platform clients, usually End Users – Stakeholders and End Users – End Users, are required to achieve some of the functional requirements defined for the platform.

A requests approach has been proposed to enable communication tracking and user data protection. A requests service has been developed, where the different required requests are defined, either with the desired associated functionalities.

Each request creates a requests object, which contains user's identification and all the required information. The request object implements methods for the execution of the requests, to accept or reject it, which can be ejected by the user with the role required in each use case.

The following sequence diagram implements the request handling process, which is adapted to each use case.

Diagram 1: Requests service API.

Survey service

The surveys system implemented on the platform is based on the SurveyJS a powerful set of libraries for handling surveys creation, management, rendering, and analysis. Together with the cloud services offered by its creators has been the framework proposed for surveys' management. Stakeholder have to create an account in SurveyJS cloud services to enable the surveys management.

Surveys are created by the different interfaces available at the EUSHP, which allow also the edition of the surveys and the access to the analysis pages. Each survey is identified by a survey id, which is the survey definition identifier, used by the platform to get the questions and render the survey to the client. It also has a post id, the identifier used when the client wants to submit a new answer to the service. The survey is rendered into the user screen with the SurveyJS API.

Diagram 2: Survey result saving into SurveyJS Service.

GRANTA Entities access

The majority of projects stakeholders' information is stored in the database management system developed by GRANTA and further covered in D6.4. In order to access the information contained in such database, a gateway has been developed to retrieve entities information. Diagram 3 defines the method to retrieve the full information about one single record of the database, method implemented into the EUSHP for the different object of the Ecobulk ecosystem.

Diagram 4 describes the sequence used to download a full set of entities from a single family, used to fill tables and searching. To improve the latency and performance on that cases, only some important attributes are retrieved from the database.

Furthermore, some entities require extra information from other context. For that reason, a children loop its included to retrieve the required information from other services. To improve the performance of these request an asynchronous event drive approach has been used. For each type of entity, a detailed sequence diagram will be defined to expose the is particularities.

Diagram 3: GRANTA database GET Entity.

Diagram 4: GRANTA database GET Entity table.

3.2.2 Non-registered users

This section describes functional requirements that do not need the client to be registered in the platform. Thus, they are mostly informative or directed to the fast and easy interaction (with less obstacles as possible) of the user with the platform (e.g. view a datasheet, answer a survey, ...)

These functional requirements are developed as specified by user stories described in the Annex A.

Product scanner

As defined at deliverable 6.2, Ecobulk products are tracked by QR codes, which can be used to identify the product and access its information. These QR codes can be scanned by any smartphone, using any native scanning applications or by the platform built-in QR scanner.

Figure 4: Platform QR Scanner.

Once the QR code has been scanned the platform loads the information about the product. It also allows the user to switch between the different available cameras on the device, and implements a rescan button once a product has been retrieved.

Diagram 5: Product scan with native client app.

If the QR code is scanned by the native QR scanner of the user, the user will be sent to the QR service defined at deliverable D6.2, which redirects the user to the EUSHP including the product id on the URL, then the application will request the product data to the appropriated service (see Diagram 5).

Diagram 6: Product scan with embedded QR reader.

Diagram 6 shows the path followed if the user scans the QR code from the platform embedded QR scanner. The product id is retrieved by following the request to the QR service.

Scanned products information

Using the product id, the application retrieves the product information and the data is shown in the user device. This process allows the user to answer the product opinion survey. If the user is logged as end user or stakeholder, more functionalities would be available.

Figure 5: Scanned product information.

Diagram 7: Product request by id.

Scanned products survey answer

Once the user has scanned the product by its QR code the product opinion survey can be accessed by the "Answer survey" button. The id for the product opinion survey is used to retrieve the survey definition, in the way it is defined at the Diagram 2. The survey is then rendered into the user screen with the SurveyJS API. At the end of the survey the results are sent back to the SurveyJS service. The user information is not saved with the survey answer on this kind of survey for privacy purposes.

Figure 6: Answer survey interface.

3.2.3 End Users and Stakeholders

The functional requirements contained in this section refer to those that users can perform with a created profile, both end users and stakeholder's roles. This section regards to the specific requirements about user authentication and management and the search open access information from the Ecobulk database.

User verification and data

Users are identified by a https secure cookie containing the user information signed by the authentication service. Once the user is inside the application a verification query is done to check if the user is logged and retrieve its identity. Then the user data is shown at the header of the interface.

Figure 7: Logged user indications on frontend.

Diagram 8: User data request and modification.

Once this request is done, if the user was properly authenticated, the following information is sent to the frontend.

- User profile
- User extra data
- Associated stakeholder data

Search published products

This view allows to users and stakeholder to explore the Ecobulk ecosystem database (hosted by GRANTA), regarding to the product types available for supply to end users. Specific information about the stakeholder associated to the product is retrieved from the Single-Sign-On service.

Product ↑	Manufacturer	Description
Cube unit	Moretti	Basic cube unit for modular furniture

Figure 8: Ecobulk products searching table.

Diagram 9: Simplified products table request.

The full list of products can be requested to the service, or only products from a specific stakeholder. To improve latencies and load times, only the necessary information is requested, full product data is lazy loaded as the user opens the product details.

Products attributes requested:

- Id
- Name

- StakeholderId
- Description

Users can filter in the products table by product name

Figure 9: Products name filter.

Products detailed information

Product details can be accessed from the table items, showing complete Granta Database product type information, in the same way as the products scanner. It also allows the owner stakeholder to update product description and some information items. It implements Diagram 7.

The screenshot displays the 'End Users & Stakeholders Platform' interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Label Scanner', 'Instances', 'Products', 'Materials', 'Surveys', and 'Logout'. The main content area shows product details for 'Storage Marshall One' by manufacturer 'ABC'. It includes a photograph of the product and a description: 'Standing or lying, against the wall or to divide the room - KALLAX series is eager to please and will adapt to your taste, space, budget and needs. Fine tune with drawers, shelves, boxes and inserts.' Below this is a 'General information' table:

General information	
Product name	Storage Marshall One
Manufacturer	ABC
Product code	rt5c4v7b98wer1t
Unit cost (new):	40 €

At the bottom, there is a 'Customer information' section.

Figure 10: Product detailed information.

Waste converters

A searching view for waste converters is available for end users and stakeholders, which show the information stored in GRANTA database, showing contact information and available processing methods. Two different view can be user, map or table.

The screenshot shows the 'End User Test' interface with a map view selected. The map displays several locations in central Italy, marked with red pins and labeled as 'dummy_record' entries: 'dummy_moretti_record', 'dummy_rilegno_record_01', 'dummy_rilegno_record_02', and 'dummy_rilegno_record_03'. The map includes a search bar at the top left with 'Mapa' and 'Satélite' options, and a navigation panel on the right. The top navigation bar includes 'Label Scanner', 'My Products', 'Products', 'Marketplace', and 'Logout'.

Figure 11: Waste converters searching map.

Name		Address	Processes		
Waste converters united	Waste group, Waste Road 3, Wastelands 12345 Germany		shredding of wood	shredding of plastics	melting of plastics
Moretti Compact S.p.A	Via Giuseppe di Vittorio, 2, 61026 Piandimeleto PU, Italia			composting	shredding of wood
Multi Green S.R.L.	Località Marischio Cà Maiano, 78, 60044 Ca' Maiano AN, Italia		shredding of wood	shredding of plastics	melting of metal
				melting of plastics	
Cosmari S.R.L.	Località Piane del Chienti, 62029 Tolentino MC, Italia		shredding of wood	melting of metal	melting of plastics

Figure 12: Waste converters searching table.

Diagram 10: Waste converters request.

Waste converters detailed information

The client can access complete waste converter information by clicking on the desired row. A pop-up window shows the data stored on GRANTA about the selected waste converter.

3.2.4 End Users

The functional requirements contained in this section refer to those that users can perform with a created end user profile. This section regards to the specific requirements about user products instances management, feedback, request, dispose or marketplace management.

Request products to stakeholders

End users can create requests of products to stakeholders by accessing the searching utility. The service is implemented with the request implementation (Diagram 1) defined at general functional requirements.

The screenshot shows the 'End User Test' interface for a product. The header includes the ECOBULK logo and navigation links: Label Scanner, My Products, Products, Marketplace, Profile, and Logout. The main content area displays a table with columns for Product, Manufacturer, and Description. The selected product is 'Cube unit' by 'Moretti', described as 'Basic cube unit for modular furniture'. Below the table, there is a product image, a description, and three buttons: 'Answer Survey', 'Request Purchase', and 'Request Leasing'. A 'Quantity' input field is set to '1'. At the bottom, a 'General information' table provides details about the product name, manufacturer, product code, and unit cost.

Product	Manufacturer	Description
Cube unit	Moretti	Basic cube unit for modular furniture

Answer Survey
 Quantity: 1
 Request Purchase
 Request Leasing

General information	
Product name	Cube unit
Manufacturer	Moretti
Product code	D2S6V3
Unit cost (new)	35 €

Figure 13: End-user own product information page with the survey and leasing buttons enabled.

Find own product instances

End users can access to their products instances by the instance table, with searching filters for product name or manufacturer and product status.

ECOBULK End Users & Stakeholders Platform				
End User Test				
Name	Manufacturer	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Service	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Marketplace	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Disused
Product ↑	Identifier	Manufacturer	Status	
Storage Marshall One	202100001			service
Storage Marshall One	202100002			service
Storage Marshall One	202100003			marketplace
Storage Marshall One	202100004			service
Storage Marshall One	202100005			disused
Storage Marshall One	202100006			marketplace

Figure 14: End user own instances searching table.

Diagram 11: End user instances, associated products and stakeholders request.

Instance attributes requested:

- Complete instance record
- Product (Simplified)
- StakeholderId

Access product instance details

Users can access to the details of each own instance and modify it.

The screenshot displays the 'End User Test' page in the ECOBULK application. The header includes the ECOBULK logo, 'Label Scanner', 'My Products', and a user profile menu. The main content area shows details for a product instance:

- Name:** Storage Marshall One
- Manufacturer:** 202100001
- Status:** service
- Business Model:** leasing
- Creation date:** 2/11/21

At the top right, there are checkboxes for 'Service' (checked), 'Marketplace' (checked), and 'Disused' (checked). Below the details, there are four buttons: 'Open Survey', 'To Marketplace', 'Disused', and 'Delete'.

Figure 15: End user instance information.

Answer product instance survey

Users can answer the instance survey defined by the stakeholder for the product. This survey can be only answer by the product instance owner, and it can be used to get information about the product status in all its life cycle.

Figure 16: End user instance survey window.

Change instance status

End user can change the status of its own instances, either by setting them as disused or by moving them to the marketplace.

Figure 17: End user instance toolbox.

Diagram 12 Instance state modification request

Marketplace requests

Requests in the marketplace for the instances of the end user can be handled in the marketplace request table. The request contains contact information of the user which has created the request, to handle the transaction (outside the scope of the EUSHP), and finally the owner can accept the request if it has been done successfully or reject it.

This service implements the request system defined before.

ECOBULK				
End User Test		Label Scanner	My Products	
		Profile	Logout	
My products		Marketplace Requests		
Product	Quantity	Contact	Actions	
Kallax	5	email@purchase.com	Sell	Reject

Figure 18: Marketplace instances buyer notification.

3.2.5 Stakeholders

The functional requirements contained in this section refer to those that users can perform with a created stakeholder profile with a valid stakeholder validated and associated. This section regards to the specific requirements about full Ecobulk environments information searching, data management, instances management and surveys creation, management and analysis.

Search published composites

Stakeholder have access to the available information about composites in the Ecobulk ecosystem, downloaded from GRANTA in the same way than products.

ECOBULK End Users & Stakeholders Platform	
Stakeholder test	Label Scanner Instances Profile Logout
Composites	
Product	Description
Compomax 01	Elastic wood reinforced composite
Compomax 02	Elastic wood reinforced composite
Compomax 03	Elastic wood reinforced composite

Figure 19: Ecobulk composites searching table.

Diagram 13: Composites table request.

To improve loading times a list of composites with simple attributes is loaded at the access to the table, which contains, for each one:

- Name
- Stakeholder
- Description

Composite details

The client can access complete composite data by clicking on the desired row. The full composite data is loaded in an emerging dialog.

General information	
Producer	Coventive
Material overview	
Material family	Thermoplastic composite
Material	PP-NF
Renewable content	%
Links	
Raw materials used to create this composite	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Polypropylene Moplen HP 500V Jute
Composition detail	
Polymer	70 %
Physical properties	
Density	950 kg/m ³
Mechanical properties	
Young's modulus	4.9 GPa
Specific stiffness	5.16 MN.m/kg
Virtual strain limit (elastic limit)	28.0 MPa

Figure 20: Composite details table.

Diagram 14: Complete composite request.

This mechanism loads all the information which is defined into the GRANTA MI Database for the desired item, avoiding empty items to improve performance.

Search published raw materials

In the same way, stakeholder can access raw materials of GRANTA MI database.

ECOBULK End Users & Stakeholders Platform		Label Scanner	Instances	
Stakeholder test		Profile	Logout	
		Composites	Raw Materials	
Product	Description			
Wood 01	Standar wood for furniture			
Wood 02	Standar wood for furniture			
Glue	Standar wood for furniture			

Figure 21: Raw materials searching table.

Diagram 15: Simplified materials request.

Information retrieved in the table loading process:

- Name
- Stakeholder
- Description

Raw material details

The client can access complete composite data by clicking on the desired row. The full raw material data is loaded in an emerging dialog.

End Users & Stakeholders Platform	
Stakeholder test	<p>General information</p> <p>Producer: LyondellBasell</p> <p>Description: Polypropylene Moplen HP 500V</p> <p>Material overview</p> <p>Material family: Thermoplastic polymer</p> <p>Material: PP</p> <p>Composition detail</p> <p>Polymer: 100 %</p> <p>Links</p> <p>Composites using this raw material:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Jute - PP LFT 1.1 Jute/GF - PP LFT 1.1 Jute/CF - PP LFT 1.1 <p>Physical properties</p> <p>Density: 910 kg/m³</p> <p>Rheological properties</p> <p>Melt flow rate (230°C/2.16kg): 120 g/10 min</p> <p>Mechanical properties</p> <p>Young's modulus: 1.45 GPa</p> <p>Yield strain: 7 % strain</p> <p>Tensile strength: 35 MPa</p>
Product	
dummy_record_do not use	
Polypropylene Moplen HP 500V	
Polypropylene Moplen HP 548R	
Polypropylene Adstif HA 840R	
Maleic anhydride Polypropylene	
Jute	
E-Glass Fibre 1200 tex	
Carbon fibre T700S-C-12K-60E	
Recycled carbon fibre (rCF)	

Figure 22: Materials details table.

Diagram 16: Complete materials request.

Complete raw material data loading its requested as desired by the client, again, reduce loading time and improve performance.

Search published designs

Stakeholder have access to the available information about designs in the Ecobulk ecosystem, downloaded from GRANTA in the same way than products.

End Users & Stakeholders Platform		
Stakeholder test	Label Scanner	Instances
	Products	Materials
	Designs	Surveys
Product	Producer	Material family
dummy_record_do_not_use	Coventive	Recycled commercial thermoplastics

Figure 23: Designs searching table.

Diagram 17: Simplified designs request.

Information retrieved in the table loading process:

- Name
- Stakeholder
- Description

Designs details

The client can access complete composite data by clicking on the desired row. The full raw material data is loaded in an emerging dialog.

General information	
Producer	Coventive
Material overview	
Material family	Recycled commercial thermoplastics
Material	ABS
Renewable content	%
End-user feedback	
Component common failure modes specified by the manufacturer and repair/refurbish processes	Component Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.
Product common failure modes specified by the manufacturer and repair/refurbish processes	Product Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit.
End-User feedback about the final product	20
Composition detail	
Wood	20 %
Polymer	80 %
Other material	Fiber

Figure 24: Designs details table.

Diagram 18: Complete designs request.

Complete raw material data loading its requested as desired by the client, again, reduce loading time and improve performance.

Product instances table

Stakeholder can access to the instances for their own products, getting a table including the product name, the identifier, the client name and the product status.

			
Stakeholder test Logout 			
	Operating Instances		Instances Requests
Product	Identifier	Client	Status
Storage Marshall One	202100001	End User Test	service
Storage Marshall One	202100002	End User Test	service
Storage Marshall One	202100003	End User Test	marketplace
Storage Marshall One	202100004	End User Test	service
Storage Marshall One	202100005	End User Test	disused
Storage Marshall One	202100006	End User Test	marketplace

Figure 25: Stakeholder instances searching table.

Diagram 19: Stakeholder instances request.

Information retrieved in the table loading process:

- Complete instance record
- Product (Simplified)
- Stakeholder
- End User

Product requests

Stakeholder can access requests from users for their published products. Inside the request information the client contact method can be found. The instances requests process, as it is not part of the stakeholder business process, require to the stakeholder to process the instance acquisition outside the platform. Once the lease or purchase is finished, stakeholder can accept the user request, and it would create a new instance for the owner.

The screenshot shows the 'End Users & Stakeholders Platform' interface. The top navigation bar includes the ECOBULK logo, 'Label Scanner', 'Instances', and a menu icon. Below this, a dark bar contains 'Stakeholder test', 'Profile', and 'Logout'. The main content area has two tabs: 'Operating Instances' and 'Instances Requests' (which is active). A table below the tabs displays instance data.

Product	Quantity	Client	Instances Requests	
			Accept	Reject
Storage Marshall One	1	End User Test	Accept	Reject

Figure 26: Instance creation requests from end users.

Survey management

Stakeholder can access to their own product types to manage the surveys associated. Each product has defined three different surveys, with a different objective each:

- Product survey – User opinion feedback
- Instance survey – Instance status evolution
- Decision support system survey – DSS conditions survey

The product survey can be answered by any person that has scanned the product QR code, with the objective of getting users feedback. The instance survey can be filled by the instance owner, and the objective is to register the degradation evolution of the product. Finally, the DSS survey is used just at the end of live of the product. The owner has to answer the survey to give feedback to the stakeholder about the actual status of the product, damages, etc, in order to run the DSS algorithm.

The result of the first two surveys can be analysed at the SurveyJS service, the last one is just show on the DSS.

To access the survey analytics, stakeholder can access in three places:

- Product search: Access to full analytics page about product survey and instance survey.
- Instance search: Access to analytics page about instance survey with instance id filter shortcut.
- Survey manager: Access to full analytics page about product survey and instance survey.

Survey results can be visualized either using the analytics toolbox, which includes some graphical view of the answers, or using the table view, where the data can be filtered or downloaded in PDF, Excel or CSV.

Figure 27: SurveyJS results analytics.

The screenshot shows the SurveyJS results table view. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the SurveyJS logo (v 1.8.60) and menu items: Our Products, Overview, My Surveys, Examples, Public API Docs, and Private API Docs. Below the navigation bar, the page title is "Survey Results for: Storage Marshall_Instance". There are three tabs: Summary (selected), Table, and Info. Below the tabs, there are buttons for PDF, Excel, and CSV, and a search bar. A "Show 5 entries" dropdown is visible. The table has five columns: question1, question2, instance, userid, and Submitted. The table contains three rows of data.

question1	question2	instance	userid	Submitted
item2	item3	["202100001"]	["5ff841e5076a50002fb328c5"]	2021-05-19T16:44:48.8942261
item1	item1	["202100001"]	["5ff841e5076a50002fb328c5"]	2021-05-19T16:35:28.6987773
item2	item3	["202100001"]	["5ff841e5076a50002fb328c5"]	2021-05-19T16:41:35.6288467

Figure 28: SurveyJS results table.

To edit the survey, model the SurveyJS creator is used. By accessing the edit button, the survey creator page is opened:

Figure 29: SurveyJS creator.

The edit button is available either at the product search page or the survey management page.

4 EXTERNAL INTERFACES REQUIREMENTS

4.1 Single-Sign-On Service

The proposed microservice architecture includes the implementation of a single sign-on authentication process. It must provide a reliable authorization service for the different applications involved on the Ecobulk environment.

4.1.1 System description

A client token stored as a secure cookie has been considered. The token provides the user identification number and role signed by the server with secure private key. The use of JSON Web Token (JWT) as a standard solution is foreseen. In general, the structure of a JWT consists of three parts, namely; header, payload signature.

The header information about content type values for JWT and details about the algorithm used by the signature. This information is essential to handle the verification of the token.

The payload is composed just by the necessary information to determine the user identity represented as a JSON object. The following data table describes the information included in the token by the SSO service.

Property name	Long name	Description
id	User identifier	Unique ObjectID defined for each user at the registration.
role	User role	Role associated with the user.

The signature consists on the public key obtained by the signature algorithm in order to verify the data contained on the payload has not been modified. It is used by the SSO service to check that a client JWT its original, so it avoids identity fraud.

To avoid Cross Site Request Forgery (CSRF), Cross Site Scripting (XSS), and Man-in-the-middle attacks the cookies are defined as secure, to be only sent to HTTPS secure hosts, accessible only by http (HttpOnly), avoiding the access by JavaScript by any malicious code, with the Same Site flag defined as Strict, avoid the token to be sent to the Ecobulk service.

4.1.2 Sign-On Requirement

The user is able to sign-on into the application by the email and password defined at the registration process. If the user came from an Ecobulk application the sign-on service will redirect him at the end of the authentication process. If the user has accesses the SSO web app directly will have to choose the desired application to get in.

The screenshot shows a login interface for Ecobulk. On the left is a teal vertical bar with the Ecobulk logo and the word 'ECOBULK' in white. The main area is white and titled 'Login'. It contains two input fields: 'Email' and 'Password'. Below the password field is a 'Remember Me' checkbox. A large, rounded 'Login' button is centered below the inputs. At the bottom, there is a link: 'Don't have an account? Register Here'.

Figure 30: Login frontend.

Diagram 20: User login jwt delivery across domains.

4.1.3 User verification Requirement

The service publishes an endpoint dedicated to the user authentication. The authentication token sent by the client to the services is used to verify and get the client identity.

Diagram 21: User verification schema.

4.1.4 Sign Up Requirement

End users and stakeholder are able to create new account into the SSO service, to be able to access Ecobulk environment applications.

The screenshot shows a 'Sign Up' form with the following fields and elements:

- First Name**: Text input field.
- Second Name**: Text input field.
- Email**: Text input field.
- Password**: Text input field.
- Password Confirm**: Text input field.
- Select Role:** A dropdown menu with 'Stakeholder' selected.
- Stakeholders Private Password**: Text input field.
- reCAPTCHA**: A widget with the text 'No soy un robot' and a 'reCAPTCHA' logo.
- Signup**: A blue button at the bottom of the form.

Figure 31: User creation frontend.

End user's role is open to be taken by any client, stakeholder accounts can only be created with a private key defined for each stakeholder. Then the account would be linked to the stakeholder profile.

Diagram 22: User creation.

To ensure the security and the privacy of user's data the following non-functional requirements had been considered:

- Data validation in frontend
 - Email format
 - Password length
- Validation, integrity and string escape in backend
- State of the art password hashing algorithms
- Google Recaptcha v2 security

4.2 GRANTA Database API Implementation

The proposed micro service architecture requires the implementation of an API Gateway to access Ecobulk GRANTA database. It has to implement the required methods to perform the required functionalities of the EU&SH Platform.

4.2.1 System description

This service objective will be to feed data requirements from the End User and Stakeholders Platforms, products, materials, waste converters and instances searching interfaces. As seen in platform requirements described, it requires an access method to extract data from the project database. It has been developed based on the MIScripting Toolkit provided by GRANTA and described at the deliverable 6.4.

Figure 32: GRANTA Database MIScripting Toolkit schema.

For the introduction of data into the database, an approach based on spreadsheets templates and importer helpers is proposed. This is intended to alleviate the need of dealing with complex database data structures or learning how to fill those fields directly on the database.

Figure 33: GRANTA Database data introduction.

5 APPLICATION OF P2B REGULATION (EU) 2019/1150

The End-User and Stakeholder platform has been adapted to the Regulation (EU) 2019/1150 published on June 20th 2019 and applicable since July 12nd 2020 on promoting fairness and transparency for business users of online intermediation services. The objective of the regulation is to contribute to the proper functioning of internal market by laying down rules to ensure that business users of online intermediation services and corporate website users in relation to online search engines are granted appropriate transparency, fairness and effective redress possibilities. This regulation is focused on online intermediation services including online e-commerce market places, online software application services and online social media services where transactions between business users and consumers take place. The regulation covers topics like:

- Terms and Conditions of the online intermediation services.
- A clear policy for the restriction, suspension or termination of the services provided.
- Transparency in the ranking of the products offered to the end-users.
- A description of any differentiated treatment afforded in relation to goods/services offered to consumers.

In this section, the articles of the regulation which apply to the End-User and Stakeholder platform and have been incorporated are exposed. The rest of the articles are not considered applicable because they are out of the scope of the platform (6, 10, 13 and 14) or related to supervision, revision and application of the regulation (15-19).

5.1 Article 3: Terms and conditions

Following the guidelines provided by the Regulation (EU) 2019/1150, the terms and conditions are drafted in plain and intelligible language and are easily available to platform users at all stages of their relationship with the provider of the online intermediation services. These terms and conditions have been included in the platform

through a link in the platform footer or in the about section of the mobile version of the platform.¹

Figure 34: Terms and conditions page in the end-user and stakeholder platform.

In case these terms and conditions are modified, the provider of the online intermediation service will notify the users of the platform of this modification. The application of the terms and conditions modification will occur at least 15 days from the date on which the provider notifies the users concerned about the proposed changes. These will have the right to terminate the contract with the provider of the online intermediation services before the expiry of the notice period. Such termination shall take effect within 15 days from the receipt of the notice. During the notice period, submitting new goods or services to the online intermediation services is considered a clear affirmative action to waive the notice period, except in cases where the reasonable and

¹ available at the following webpage: <https://eushp.ecobulk.upc.edu/termsAndConditions>.

proportionate notice period is longer than 15 days because the changes to the terms and conditions require the business user to make significant technical adjustments to its goods or services.

Apart from the clearness of the terms and conditions, in order to further enhance the transparency of the platform, the business users providing products or services on the online intermediation services, including ECOBULK partners, are clearly identified.

5.2 Article 4: Restriction, suspension and termination

In the exploitation phase of the platform, the guidelines presented in Article 4 of the regulation will be applied for the restriction, suspension and termination of actions and/or relationships. In case the provider of the online intermediation service restricts or suspends its services to a given user, the provider will facilitate the user with a statement of reasons for the decision. If the provider decides to terminate the provision of the complete online intermediation service, the statement of reasons will be provided at least 30 days prior the termination taking effect.

In these cases, the business providers will have the opportunity to clarify the facts and circumstances occurred through an internal complaint-handling process, which is specified in section 5.7 of this document.

5.3 Article 5: Ranking

According to Article 5 of the regulation, the terms and conditions exposed in section 5.1 should include the conditions and main parameters determining ranking and reason for the relative importance of those main parameters as opposed to other parameters. For the developed End-User and Stakeholder platform, no ranking based on relative importance is performed. Instead, products are presented by default following a first-in first-out (FIFO) method. This information is included in the terms and conditions of the platform and is available to platform users and business users of the online intermediation services at all process stages.

5.4 Article 7: Differentiated treatment

According to the regulation, any differentiated treatment given to goods or services offered through the online intermediation service should be clearly stated in the terms and conditions of the platform. The End-User and Stakeholder platform do not provide any type of differentiated treatment, which has been reflected in the terms and conditions of the online service.

5.5 Article 8: Specific contractual terms

In order to establish relationships based on fair dealing, the provider of the End-User and Stakeholder platform will:

- Not impose retroactive changes to terms and conditions except if required by legal or regulatory obligation or when these changes are beneficial for the users of the platform.
- Ensure that the conditions to terminate the relationship of users with the platform are clearly stated in the terms and conditions.
- Include in the terms and conditions a description of the technical and contractual access to the information provided or generated by the users, which is maintained after the expiry of the contract between the provider of the service and the user.

5.6 Article 9: Access to data

According to Article 9 of the regulation, the terms and conditions should include a description of the technical and contractual access of business users to any personal or other data which other business users or consumers provide for the use of the online intermediation service. This access to data information is carried out without prejudice to the application of Regulation (EU) 2016/679, Directive (EU) 2016/680 and Directive 2002/58/EC. For the End-User and Stakeholder platform.

Figure 35: Personal data treatment section of the terms and conditions of the End-User and Stakeholders platform.

5.7 Article 11: Internal complaint-handling systems

Following the guidelines provided in Article 11 of the regulation, an internal system for handling the complaints of all users of the End-User and Stakeholder Platform has been developed. This internal complaint-handling system is easily accessible and free of charge, assuring the complaint handling within a reasonable time. Any complaints are processed internally and have to be sent to the following email address: complaint-handling.ecobulk@upc.edu.

To show the well-functioning and effectiveness of the complaint handling system, a newsletter providing insights and statistics about the number of complaints issued, solved and the estimated time of response will be scheduled annually or when significant changes are needed. The process to handle the complaints is included in the terms and conditions of the platform.

5.8 Article 12: Mediation

Article 12 of the regulation will be applied in the exploitation phase of the End-User and Stakeholder platform beyond the ECOBULK project. During the execution of the project, given the direct relationship between the platform and the consortium, the mediation will take place as specified in the Consortium Agreement:

“Any dispute, controversy or claim arising under, out of or relating to this contract and any subsequent amendments of this contract, including, without limitation, its formation,

validity, binding effect, interpretation, performance, breach or termination, as well as non-contractual claims, shall be submitted to mediation in accordance with the WIPO Mediation Rules. The place of mediation shall be Brussels unless otherwise agreed upon. The language to be used in the mediation shall be English unless otherwise agreed upon. If, and to the extent that, any such dispute, controversy or claim has not been settled pursuant to the mediation within 60 calendar days of the commencement of the mediation, it shall, upon the filing of a Request for Arbitration by either Party, be referred to and finally determined by arbitration in accordance with the WIPO Expedited Arbitration Rules. Alternatively, if, before the expiration of the said period of 60 calendar days, either Party fails to participate or to continue to participate in the mediation, the dispute, controversy or claim shall, upon the filing of a Request for Arbitration by the other Party, be referred to and finally determined by arbitration in accordance with the WIPO Expedited Arbitration Rules. The place of arbitration shall be Brussels unless otherwise agreed upon. The language to be used in the arbitral proceedings shall be English unless otherwise agreed upon.”

This information has been included in the terms and conditions of the End-User and Stakeholder Platform.

6 USE CASE EXAMPLE

On this section some use cases examples are shown with their current implementation in the EUSHP application. This use case screenshots are particularly referred to the automotive sector demonstrator developed by MICROCAB in WP4 (last outcomes presented in D4.5) and supported by the business model developed and reported in WP8 deliverables.

6.1 Anonymous user product opinion

- User want to submit its feedback about a product stored in the EUSHP which it is not owned by the user. First, the user must identify the QR sticker or plate in the product and scan it using the QR code scanner.

Figure 36: QR scanner built in the platform.

- Scanned product information: The product information is gathered from the database and served to the user through the EUSHP.

General information

Figure 37: Vianova car information page in the EUSHP.

- Access product opinion survey: As part of the information page, there are several buttons related to different surveys. The user must click one of this buttons to answer a survey and give feedback about the product.

Figure 38: Vianova car survey.

- Submit the survey by the complete button. The user completes the survey by clicking the complete button. The survey is then stored in the surveyJS platform and can be later access by the product manager.

Figure 39: Vianova car survey completion page.

6.2 Product instance request

- User search for a product which wants to buy. In this use case, the user wants to request an instance of a product. The platform provides a way to engage and connect the users with the product manufacturer.

Figure 40: Marketplace page in the EUSHP.

- Gets its information and the option to buy one or more products (the product can be available in batches of instances)

Figure 41: Information page of the VIANOVA car.

- The user can request the product to the manufacturer on any of the business models available

Figure 42: Request product successful dialog.

- The new request is shown on the stakeholder's panel, along with the user contact information to process the request, which is out of the scope of the EUSHP

Stakeholder test

End Users & Stakeholders Platform

Label Scanner Instances

Profile Logout

Operating Instances Instances requests

Waiting Accepted Rejected

Product	Quantity	Client	Status	Actions
Storage Marshall	1	End User Test	accepted	
Storage Marshall	1	End User Test	accepted	
Vianova	1	End User Test	accepted	
Vianova	1	End User Test	waiting	Accept Reject

Figure 43: Marketplace stakeholder's panel.

- Once the stakeholder accepts the request the new instance is created

Stakeholder test

Profile Logout

Operating Instances Instances requests

Waiting Accepted Rejected

Product	Quantity	Client	Status	Actions
Storage Marshall	1	End User Test	accepted	
Storage Marshall	1	End User Test	accepted	
Vianova	1	End User Test	accepted	
Vianova	1	End User Test	accepted	

Stakeholder test

Profile Logout

Operating Instances Instances requests

Product	Identifier	Client	Status	Actions
Storage Marshall	61379f0ee5302472ccce6d16	End User Test	Service	Analyze
Storage Marshall	6137a07e4a7fa32c9830152b	End User Test	Service	Analyze
Vianova	6139e07660bda991089dfe01	End User Test	Service	Analyze
Vianova	6139e18860bda991089dfe03	End User Test	Service	Analyze

Figure 44: Marketplace stakeholder's panel after creating the new instance.

- The end user is able to answer the maintenance survey, move the product to the marketplace or disable the instance.

The screenshot shows the 'End Users & Stakeholders Platform' dashboard. The top navigation bar includes 'Label Scanner', 'My Products', and 'Marketplace'. The main content area is titled 'My products' and contains a table with columns for 'Name', 'Manufacturer', 'Service', 'Marketplace', and 'Disused'. Below the table, there are three buttons: 'Open Survey', 'To Marketplace', and 'Disused'.

Name	Manufacturer	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Service	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Marketplace	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Disused
Storage Marshall	61379f0ee5302472ccce6d16	ABC		
Storage Marshall	6137a07e4a7fa32c9830152b	ABC		
Vianova	6139e07660bda991089dfe01	Microcab		
Vianova	6139e18860bda991089dfe03	Microcab		

Business Model: Buy
Creation date: 9/8/21

Buttons: Open Survey, To Marketplace, Disused

Figure 45: New survey enabled in the dashboard that corresponds to the maintenance survey.

7 CONCLUSIONS

This document presents an approach to features and functionalities required by the different profiles in an example of circular supply-chain economy framework. Furthermore, it includes a review of the formal aspects, general functionalities and software requirements for the features proposed as the End users and Stakeholder platform for the Ecobulk project.

The document includes the definition of the user roles, an in-depth study of the needs and requirements of the participants from the point of view of use cases, and a detailed approach to the subsequent functions and features required, defining the frontend and backend specifications for the different services proposed.

However, it must be noted that the end-user & Stakeholder platform has been created as a demonstrator of the services that can be developed around a circular supply chain. It has to be seen as a pilot platform created in the Ecobulk project, with the usual limitations that a pilot example has, but not limited to the Ecobulk project, therefore other stakeholders and users could make use of its structure of the functionalities defined in it to build its own service or even adhere to the Ecobulk's platform ecosystem.

8 ANNEX A – PROFILES AND USE CASES

8.1 End user

Profile

- A person or institution (e.g University) that wants to get rid of decking, fencing, or any other light and temporary construction or garden structures (e.g. utility sheds, shelters, terrace roofing, etc.) made of composites
- Looking for ways to get rid of waste at little cost, quickly and without too much effort
- If possible, to get some paid back, but not essential
- Moderate sustainability/environmental concerns

Staff

- Member of staff living inside or outside campus
- Limited sustainability/environmental concerns – facing time pressure
- Moderate sustainability/environmental concerns – although facing time pressure because of landlord limitations
- High sustainability/environmental concerns – looking for local repair/reuse shops within her local area

Student

- Student living inside or outside campus
- Could have moderate sustainability/environmental concerns – although facing time pressure because of landlord limitations, or high sustainability/environmental concerns – looking for local options

Expected outcomes from the platform

- Quick, easy to use – mobile compatible
- Options for selling / giving away / disposing it

Information about the value of waste, if any, and costs of different disposing options

- Logistics arrangements / collection preferable it as it is more comfortable
- Information about environmental impact of different disposing options

Id	I want to	so that	Notes
Registered user and owner			
1 - Create a product instance from ecobulk products available			
1.1	Create a profile	People can link the resource to a specific company and location	It would be better if the company/person can create the post first and then invited to create a profile before submitting it
1.2	Search for products from providers and get detailed information	I can evaluate the purchase of sustainable products and participate in circular economi processes	
1.3	Create a product request	Provider can contact with the user to sell the products and continue the tracking process of the product	The user should be able to extract most information from the platform passport database by scanning the bar or QR code of the product.
1.4	Get my inventory, track my product instances, and monitor its state.	I can get a better idea of how my item/components health status, information end evolution.	Product detailed informations, tracking and survey results can provide these functions.

2 - Product state feedback

2.1	Give feedback about the product state and maintenance	I can get advices about the best way to manage my product.	The platform will allow to purchasers end user to give feedback using surveys defined by the stakeholder.
2.2	Receive a list of preliminary potential routes for disposal and their impact	Have an idea of potential outcomes from the beginning	Stakeholder, by the DSS and surveys data can give the best options to the end users about the selling/giving away/disposal

3 - Identify potencial ways of give away/dispose

3.1	Be able to see on a map or list the already available options	Have a quick feedback on alternative valorisation alternatives for my products	It could be important that the user have a quick preliminary idea of options.
3.2	Be contacted by the platform with a list of options for my waste/resources	I can compare the different options and select the one I would like to pursue	

4 - Maintenance of a product

4.1	Have access to product manuals	I can maintain and repair the product myself.	
4.2	Have documentation regarding the product's use, environmental conditions and repairs	I can estimate the residual value of the product and perform preventive maintenance.	

4.3	Have information about spares & upgrades	I know what I can do with my product if it is damaged or if I want to adjust it.
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5 - Repair/revalorize/recicle a product

5.1	Know about collection points	I can take a product there when I want to repair it, sell it or discard it.
5.2	Have access to disassembly instructions or waste converter requirements	Te efficiency of the process can be improven
5.3	Know the options to repair or remanufacture a given product	I can extend the life cycle of the product by using it longer.

6 - Sell/reuse a product

6.1	Have access to a product marketplace of used instances	I can look for reusable options or evaluate if it is possible to reuse my products	
6.2	Contact with published product owner	I can get an arrangement to purchase the product	The user can create a request for a product published in the marketplace to be able to contact with owner
6.3	Publish my own instances to the marketplace	I can sell my products as a way to increase its sustainability and get a payback.	

6.4	Recive product request from other user for my published products	I can contact with them to reach an agreement	The user, once have sold the product, can accept the product purchase request on its notifications.
6.5	Change the product instance owner	Ensure the continuity of the tracking process and the circularity of the product	

Product end user (not owner)

Id	I want to	so that	Notes
1 - Scan ecobulk product			
1.1	Scan a product I am currelty ussing	I can learn about the origin of the product and the ecobulk environment	
1.2	Give feedback about the product	I can collaborate in the improvement of a product or place, also with the circular economy.	

8.2 Designers, FEA engineers

Profile

- Engineering companies, research centers, universities with design and structural knowledge
- Looking for new ways of collaboration and create partnerships

Expected outcomes from the platform

- Achieve new arrangements with product manufacturers
- Access to sustainable materials and processes database
- Get feedback for the designs

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
1 - Material information			
1.1	Have access to available materials and their properties	I can ensure the design accomplishes the expected product's properties and cost.	Costs, usage constraints, environmental impact.
1.2	Ensure I am using Material Cards updated and approved by Material Experts	I can perform high quality simulations.	The material cards must include both technical and safety data sheet.
1.3	Have information about failure modes of similar existing products	I can anticipate them in the design to prevent failures.	
1.4	Know information such as the dimensions, structural quality, etc. of the end of	I can sort them and select those that are suitable for the new product	The availability of this information determines what is the residual value of the product

use components that I'm planning to reuse

1.5 Have access to the quantities of the available materials

I can make sure there is sufficient quantity available for production.

When choosing a recycled material, it is important that there is enough for production.

2 - Feedback from other circular chain actors

2.1

Receive feedback about product acceptance from manufacturers, users and dismantlers

I may improve future designs for better circularity.

Suitability, issues, defects.

2.2

Have access to wear and degradation feedback from the products

I can adjust the design and material selection to prevent these type of damage

Surface degradation, wearing, UV resistance.

3 - Business models

3.1

Have access to information about the available recovery procedures

The design can enable necessary interventions (e.g. sharing, disassembly) by means of fastener selection, chemical composition, etc.

3.2

Know about the intended business models of the product to be designed

The design can enable the necessary interventions.

For example, to allow sharing, disassembly, etc.

8.3 Material experts

Profile

- Material researcher, QA, interested in new sustainable materials and processes.
- Looking for new ways of collaboration and create partnerships

Expected outcomes from the platform

- Access to a new materials ecosystem with sustainable considerations.
- Publish and manage materials.

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
1 - Material information			
1.1	Create a profile to access to the platform	I can manage my own materials	
1.2	Be able to query materials information from the database	I can extract material property parameters.	
1.3	Be able to modify parameters and import data into the database	Create or update the properties of materials according to my expertise or tests performed.	

8.4 Materials manufacturer

Profile

- Sustainable product manufacturers
- Composite product manufacturers with GFRP production waste
- Composite extruding companies looking to develop new product lines for customers that demand environmentally beneficial products
- Composite product manufacturers responding to customer pressure to find end of life solutions to composite products
- Aware of sustainability and circular economy issues, building green image by providing sustainable solution for solving waste problems
- Interested to enhance recoverability/recyclability of its product at the EoL (labelling & tracing)

Expected outcomes from the platform

- Information about the location, quantity, weight/volume, cost of materials (if any), including extracting material passport information
- Possibility to communicate with the material passport database and ability to track & trace materials.

Id	I want to...	so that...	Notes
1.1	Search of preliminary material supply options	The company could compare different possibilities considering the location, quantity, weight/volume, cost of materials (if any), including material passport information	The platform lists all possible options based on the preliminary filtering

1.2	Search product I am interested in the marketplace	The company knows the offer of the products and can contact with owners.
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2 - Track & trace

2.1	Be able to connect labelled components with the resources passports database	The components could be traced back through their life cycle in order to enhance their recyclability at the EoL, and to be able to predict where, when and how many materials will become available in the future	The material/component passport database should be able to communicate with QR identifiers.
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3 - Buy/take back

3.1	Request to users offering products for a purchase	Create oportunities of waste to revalorize income
3.2	Contact with the user to get a agreement	Purchase products, materials or components

8.5 Manufacturers and Retailers

Profile

- A product supplier, it could be directly a manufacturer or a retailer
- Looking for ways of expanding
- Considering sustainability either as part of their vision/mission or as key component adding to their marketing strategy
- Curious to pilot other business models that could lead to new revenues: Leasing, subscription
- Looking for long term relationships
- Interested to know the market value of the waste generated because of the current spare cuts
- If paid back not possible, looking for cost-saving opportunities (to get rid of the waste at a cost lower than landfilling)
- Sustainability conscious, interested to get rid of waste considering sustainability

Retailer

- Interested to know the market value of used furniture items or the material that can be recovered. This could become important if the retailer ends taking back the furniture

Expected outcomes from the platform

- Quick, easy to use – mobile compatible
- Creation of long-lasting relationships for furniture supply to medium/large organizations (i.e. Universities, schools, hotels and similar, corporate offices, etc)
- A potential new revenue stream through product-service models
- Searcher of local end of life alternatives around their factories/facilities to minimize transport environmental impact, thus economics.
- Information about the value of waste

- Options for selling / giving away / disposing waste ensuring high value use of waste
- Quantification of environmental and social impact of different valorization routes

Id	I want to	so that	Notes
1 - Material Information			
1.1	Have access to available materials, their properties and performance, quality standards, restrictions and legislation, market acceptance	I can apply the suitable manufacturing methodology.	Data supplied by material manufacturers at Granta Database
1.2	Have access to a list of suppliers for the material	I can evaluate the supply chain stability and the business risks	
2 - Feedback from other circular chain actors			
2.1	Receive feedback from the assembler	I can adjust the component's properties and improve the manufacturing process.	
3 – Add a product into the ecobulk environment			
3.1	Create a profile on the app	People can identify the brand	
3.2	Contact with the platforma administration to create a new product into Granta database.	Send information about item is provided in a standardised format (e.g.type of product,	

condition, weight/volume,
cost, location, etc.)

4 - Identify potential opportunities for revenue

4.1	See my items posted on the platform and how it compares with similar products	
4.2	Offer my product on market places under different options - sell and/or lease	I can have a preliminary idea whether there is market interest for my product and the
4.3	See furniture that is being circulated	As a retailer decided if I am interested in taking back some furniture

5 - Review

5.1	Provide review of the entire process	People could get feedback and confidence on the users of the platform
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8.6 Logistics

Profile

- A local logistics company looking for market opportunities which creates partnership with other stakeholders of the platform.
- Willing to support other business models: leasing, subscription by providing the reverse logistic service
- Having technical skills and capabilities to collect and transport different type of materials (including potentially toxic waste)
- Looking to promote themselves as an environmentally friendly company due to bad promotion of transport carbon emissions
- Looking for long-term relationships with large facilities using ecobulk products

Expected outcomes from the platform

- Quick, easy to use – mobile compatible
- Develop long-lasting relationships with facility managers
- Identify and classify the product
- Perceived risk for the seller, buyer and user
- Structural capacity of the product
- Prevent damage due to bad storage conditions and contamination from other products
- Stability and risks of the supply chain

1 - Product information

1.1	Have access to the history and properties of a product	I can identify and classify the product. I can reduce the perceived risk for the seller, buyer and useR. I can assess the	Damage history, repair actions, supply chain data. Repairs may not be visible from outside
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		structural capacity of the product (using its repair history)	
1.2	Have access to information about the origin of the product	I can use it as a selling point	Use of conflict-free materials
1.3	Know the storage conditions and toxicity	I can prevent damage due to bad storage conditions and contamination from other products	
1.4	Have access of a list of suppliers for a specific product	I can evaluate the stability and risks of the supply chain	

8.7 Collection

Profile

- Waste collection and management company interested or contracted to take back used GFRP composite products or other composite waste materials from refurbishment or "strip out" projects
- A professional (designer/architect/contractor) that is looking for ways to reuse products and components in architectural/engineering projects, interested in incorporating old composite structures within buildings as a regular feature (e.g. cut into tiles?),
- Looking for new business opportunities, charging for the service of taking EoL waste
- Sustainability conscious, interested to get rid of waste considering sustainability
- Looking for long-term relationships

Expected outcomes from the platform

- Receiving notification from the platform of different waste product/component/material supply options based on predefined criteria (e.g. material type, quantity, grade, location radius, cost, etc.)
- Information about the location, quantity, size/weight/volume, cost of products/components/materials, including extracting material passport information
- List of logistics options with costs, time and possible environmental impacts (depends on the location of waste products)
- Logistics, legal and contractual arrangements

Id	I want to	so that	Notes
1 - Look for waste products, components, materials			
1.1	Create a profile for the company.	Can get access to the ecobulk ecosystem.	
1.2	Search waste product from the ecobulk instances	Look for new opportunities of	
1.3	Have access to product and material properties information	I know the recycling value if the product recovery is unfeasible	
2 - Product Information			
2.1	Have information regarding what products to process	I can optimize the route.	Source location, destination, weight.
2.2	Know the storage conditions and toxicity	I can prevent damage due to bad storage conditions and contamination from other products	

8.8 Re-manufacturer

Profile

- A company looking for low-cost and high-quality raw materials opportunities
- A company providing solutions for processing waste materials and converting them into secondary raw materials (e.g. pellets for injection moulding, extrusion or compression moulding) for customers that demand environmentally beneficial products recoverable at the end of life
- Aware of sustainability and circular economy issues, building green image by providing sustainable solution for solving waste problems
- Offering solutions where product take back is needed
- Looking for long-term relationships with a supplier, although multi-sourcing strategy also an option

Expected outcomes from the platform

- Search for possible material supply options based on predefined criteria (e.g. material type, quantity, grade, location radius, cost, etc.)
- Information about the location, quantity, weight/volume, cost of materials (if any), including extracting material passport information
- Possibility to expose their refurbished products
- Contact with manufacturers to find new economical arrangements

Id	I want to	so that	Notes
1 - Product Information			
1.1	Being a repair service, know the history of a product or component.	I can adjust the repair process.	

1.2	Being a refurbisher, know the history of a product or component	I can adjust the refurbishing process.
1.3	Being a remanufacturer, know the history of a product or component	I can adjust the remanufacturing process

2 - Identify potential products for remanufacturing

2.1	Search for products, components and materials of the ecosystem	I know the products circulated at the platform
2.2	Search at the marketplace for products in ways to dispose	The company could compare different possibilities considering the location, quantity, weight/volume, cost of materials (if any), including material passport information

3 - Buy/take back

3.1	Request to users offering products for a purchase	Create oportunities of waste to revalorize income
3.2	Contact with the user to get a agreement	Purchase products, materials or components

8.9 Waste converters

Profile

- Waste Management Company taking back composite waste and looking for potential buyers for this waste (new market opportunities)
- A professional (designer/architect/contractor) that is looking for ways to revalorize products and components into new materials.
- Looking for new business opportunities, charging for the service of taking EoL waste
- Sustainability conscious, interested to get rid of waste considering sustainability

Expected outcomes from the platform

- Information about the value of waste
- Information about the location, quantity, size/weight/volume, cost of products/components/materials, including extracting material passport information
- Options for selling / giving away / disposing waste ensuring high value use of waste
- Quantification of environmental and social impact of different routes

Id	I want to	so that	Notes
1 - Look for waste products, components, materials			
1.1	Create a profile for the company.		Can get access to the ecobulk ecosystem.
1.2	Search waste product from the ecobulk instances		Look for new opportunities of

2 - Identify potential products for revalorization

2.1	Search for products, components and materials of the ecosystem	I know the products circulated at the platform
2.2	Search at the marketplace for products in ways to dispose	The company could compare different possibilities considering the location, quantity, weight/volume, cost of materials (if any), including material passport information

3 - Buy/take back

3.1	Request to users offering products for a purchase	Create oportunies of waste to revalorize income
3.2	Contact with the user to get a agreement	Purchase products, materials or components